

ThrombUS+ Study B2 Lower Limb Activity Data Collection Manual

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Horizon Innovation Action | Agreement No. 101137227
HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Co-funded by the European Union

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ThrombUS+ is an Innovation Action Project co-funded by the European Union, under HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05 “Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery”.

Document Control Page**Project**

Grant Agreement:	101137227
Acronym:	Thrombus+
Title:	Wearable Continuous Point-of-Care Monitoring, Risk Estimation and Prevention for Deep Vein Thrombosis
Type:	Innovation Action
Start:	1 January 2024
End:	30 June 2027
Programme:	Horizon Europe
Call Identifier:	HORIZON-HLTH-2023-TOOL-05-05
Call Topic	Harnessing the potential of real-time data analysis and secure Point-of-Care computing for the benefit of person-centred health and care delivery
Website:	http://thrombus.eu/

Revision History			
Version	Date	Modification	Contributors
0.1	15 Jul 2025	New content - Outline	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA]
0.2	17 Jul 2025	New content – Added tables with exercises	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], P. Papageorgiou [ATHENA], K. Tzatzimaki [ATHENA], M. Liapi [ATHENA], G. Drosatos [ATHENA], N. Portokallidis [ATHENA], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]]
0.3	20 Jul 2025	Updated photos	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA]
0.4	29 Jul 2025	Removed section with exercises' step-by-step description	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA]
0.5	19 Sep 2025	Updated exercise lists	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA]

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Cite this Document as

Didaskalou S, Papageorgiou P, Tzatzimaki K, Liapi M, Portokallidis N, Drosatos G, Kaldoudi E, ThrombUS+ Study B2 Lower Limb Activity Data Collection Manual, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 29 Jul 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16915308>

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
XR	Extended Reality
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
SDK	Software Development Kit
ML/DL	Machine Learning/ Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit

Executive Summary

Study B2 is a single-centre observational, non-significant risk, training data collection study that aims to collect lower limb activity data using commercial inertial measurement units (IMUs) from healthy volunteers while performing physiotherapy exercises. In parallel cameras will be used to record the activity of the lower limbs. The collected data will be used to inform an extended reality environment (XR) and a serious game for the empowerment and guidance of post-operative patients in the clinical ward to perform their prescribed physiotherapy exercises for the prevention of DVT. Activity data will be recorded with commercially available sensors placed at specific positions of the lower limbs and commercially video cameras placed in still positions in the room. Recorded data will be anonymized and videos will only record views from below the pelvis. This document describes in detail the steps to be followed for recording the activity data from healthy volunteers while performing the physiotherapy exercises.

1. Introduction

This document outlines in detail the steps to be followed for the collection of lower limb activity data, as described in the ThrombUS+ Study B2 protocol. The study protocol describes the acquisition of lower limb activity data from healthy individuals while performing various physiotherapy exercises. These exercises are indicated for rehabilitation and DVT prevention after various surgeries or trauma. The primary objective of the study is to collect and curate lower limb activity data using Inertial Measurement Units, to inform an extended reality (XR) environment and a serious game for the empowerment and guidance of patients on performing the prescribed exercises. An anonymized dataset containing IMU data and video recordings will be created for research purposes, including the development of AI/ML models for activity recognition. All anonymised data will be published online.

Recording Studio, a python-based user interface was developed specifically to facilitate data acquisition for the abovementioned purpose. The application is capable to connect and record data from up to six Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) and two web cameras. Inertial Measurement Units are mounted on both limbs, one per limb segment (i.e. thigh, leg, foot) for recording orientation (quaternions), 3-axis linear acceleration, 3-axis angular velocity and 3-axis magnetic field strength data. The need of two cameras is required to record video data from two different angles. Cameras' field of view focus on the lower body of the participants to ensure that the whole range of motion is capture and in parallel no facial data are capture, to maintain the anonymity of the volunteers.

The application supports the use of the commercially available Movella DOT IMU sensors (Figure 1). The application utilizes the Software Development Kit (SDK) provided by Movella for connecting, synchronizing, retrieving and fusing data from all connected the sensors.

Figure 1. Movella DOT Inertial Measurement Unit. The positions of LED, power button and the micro-USM port for charging are shown. The sensor-fixed coordinate system is also shown¹.

The application is organized in three different tabs. The “Main” tab is where live data are streamed and visualized, the “Settings” tab, where sensors can be controlled and configures and the “Visualization” tab in which supports the visualization of the recorded data for inspection and validation. All tabs are accessible through the top menu bar of the application.

Participants' demographics, such as age, sex and race as well as body composition measurements will be acquired prior performing the activity exercises.

The following manual is intended for researchers conducting the study and managing the data collection procedures. It is highly recommended to follow the steps precisely to minimize errors and ensure data integrity.

2. Description of the exercises

¹ <https://www.movella.com/hubfs/Movella%20DOT%20User%20Manual.pdf>

Based on the leg involvement and the inclusion or not of a pausing phase during the execution of the exercise, different variations of the same exercise can be defined. Each exercise must be categorized as Continuous or Intermittent **and** as Left/Right (single leg) or Both. Table 1 explains the various categories.

Table 1. Categorization of exercises.

Categories	Description
Pause inclusion	
Continuous:	The exercise is performed with a continuous flow.
Intermittent:	The exercise is performed with a few seconds pause in a specific phase of the exercise.
Leg involvement	
Left/Right (single leg):	The exercise is performed using only one leg at a time, e.g. left or right
Both:	The exercise is performed using both legs simultaneously

Based on these categories each exercise must be labeled with a unique label ID to differentiate the execution variation of the exercise. Table 2 summarizes the available label IDs.

For exercises labelled either as Single or as Alternating, it is highly advised to start the left leg and continue with the right leg. The proper execution of all the exercises along their variation IDs are listed in Table 2. All listed exercise variations are also listed within the recording studio application with their unique label ID.

Table 2. List of available label IDs.

Labels	Label ID	Description
Continuous – Single	CL	The exercise is performed with a continuous flow, only the left leg is involved.
	CR	The exercise is performed with a continuous flow, only the right leg is involved.
Continuous – Both	CB	The exercise is performed with a continuous flow, both legs are involved simultaneously.
Intermittent – Single	IL	The exercise is performed with a few seconds pause in a specific phase of the exercise, only the left leg is involved.
	IR	The exercise is performed with a few seconds pause in a specific phase of the exercise, only the right leg is involved.
Intermittent – Both	IB	The exercise is performed with a few seconds pause in a specific phase of the exercise, both legs are involved simultaneously.

3. Connection and configuration of sensors

The table below (Table 3) describes the steps that are required to initialize the application, connect and configure properly the sensors, including the web cameras. Ensuring that all steps has been performed successfully is critical for acquiring high quality data.

Table 3. Steps for setting up the application by configuring connected sensors.

Step	Description	Photo
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- 1 Connect the external Bluetooth Antenna on the USB port located on the left side of the computer, as indicated in the picture with the red square.

If the external antenna is activated properly, antenna's LED will flash blue light.

If the external Bluetooth device is not activated restart the computer while keeping the antenna plugged-in.

- 2 Connect the two external cameras via the USB cables on the right USB ports of the computer.
- 3 Run the "Start Recording_recording.bat" located on the desktop to start the Recording Studio application.

- 4 Once application loads, first navigate to the "Settings" tab (1). After, press the "Read Cameras" button on the top-left of application's window and wait until all available cameras are detected (2). A list with all the available cameras will be created below the "Read Cameras" button in green (3).

If no cameras are detected, check the USB cables of the cameras and ensure they are connected properly and try to reconnect again. If the problem insists restart the computer and repeat the steps above.

- After establishing a successful connection with the cameras, navigate to the “Main” tab. Under the “Camera Views” panel (1), select which camera will serve as the “Front View” camera and which as the “Side View” camera, using the two dropdown menus (2), respectively. The “Start/Stop streaming” button can be used to select the appropriate cameras and to validate its good performance.

- Power on all the required IMU sensors by slightly pressing their “On/Off” button for a few seconds. Their LED should flash yellow light every second, indicating that the sensor is ready to be connected through Bluetooth.

- Navigate to the “Settings” tab. In the “IMU Sensor Control” panel (1), set the frame rate frequency to 30Hz, using the dropdown menu (2). Press the “Connect Sensors” button (3) and wait a few seconds for the connection to be established. A list with all available sensors along their battery status will appear on the middle-left side of the application (4). If a sensor has low battery (<20%) it is suggested to be replaced with another one.

Press the “Disconnect Sensors” button (5) and repeat steps 6 and 7 with the new sensors on.

The LED of connected sensors will flash green light once every 10 seconds.

- Place all the sensors nearby. Press the “Synchronize” button to initiate the synchronization process. This process requires around 15 seconds to be completed. Ensure that sensors have been synchronized successfully. If synchronization is completed successfully, all sensors will blink very quick and synchronously for 3 seconds.

If synchronization fails, this step can be repeated. If sensors fail to synchronize after multiple attempts, try to restart sensors and repeat steps 7 to 8.

- 9 In the “IMU Sensors Configuration” panel (1) assign a sensor to each leg segment using the drop-down menus (see section 4.3 below). Press the “Lock configuration” button when finished.

If configuration should change, press the “Unlock configuration” button first and then modify the configuration. Lock the configuration again.

- 10 Place sensors in the charging unit. Navigate to application’s “Main”. In the “IMU Vector View” panel (1), press the “Start/Stop Streaming” button (2), to start streaming orientation data from the sensors. Move the sensors and ensure the legs from the human pose move.

Place the charging unit and the extra sensor parallel, so all sensors have the same heading and remain parallel the ground.

While sensors stream data, press the “Reset Heading” button (3). Heading reset should only take place while sensors are streaming data.

Ensure that reset heading has been performed successfully.

Press the “Start/Stop Streaming” button to stop streaming data.

If reset heading did not perform successfully, repeat the abovementioned steps.

4. Data collection

The following phases involve healthy volunteers and should **only** be performed once the volunteer has been informed for the study according to Section I: Information for participants in the research project, has agreed to participate in the study and has signed Section II: Consent, of the informed consent form (ICF).

Once the volunteer signs the informed consent form (ICF), the volunteer is eligible to participate in the study. The study investigator should fill out the inclusion and exclusion criteria. If all inclusion criteria are met and all exclusion criteria are not met, then data collection phases can be performed, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Data acquisition phases.

Phase	Description
1	Acquisition of demographics.
2	Acquisition of body composition measurements.
3	Sensor mounting.

4	Activity recording.
5	Release of volunteer.

Researchers conducting the study should always be aware that the volunteers maintain the right to withdraw their consent at any time, resulting in the immediate termination of the data collection process at any step.

Estimated required time per participant: **60 minutes**

4.1. Acquisition of demographics

According to the submitted case report form (CRF) the following demographic data should be recorded:

1. Sex at birth.
2. Age.
3. Race.

4.2. Acquisition of body composition measurements

According to the submitted case report form (CRF) the following body composition measurements should be recorded:

1. Weight (in kg).
2. Height (in cm).
3. Thigh circumference (in cm).
4. Foot size (in cm).

4.3. Sensor placing

This section describes how to place the sensors on the leg segments of the volunteers. Use the straps provided by Movella and the sensor holders attached on them to fix them properly. Use the longest straps for the thighs, the mid-sized straps for the leg, and the shortest straps for the foot (Figure 2).

First, fix straps such that sensor holders are positioned on the-anterior side of the thigh and the leg, and the dorsal side of the foot, respectively, along the middle of each segment. When placing the straps, ensure that sensor holders are placed as parallel as possible, to the bone coordinate system of each segment, so the x-axis of the sensors align with the x-axis of the bone segments as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 2. The Movella straps to be used along the holders for mounting the Movella DOT IMUs .

Figure 3. Bone coordinate systems of the three leg segments of the right lower limb.

After fixing the straps, place the sensors to the holder of the appropriate leg segment, based on the configuration in the “IMU Sensor Configuration” panel in the Recording Studio application. The final placing of straps and sensors is shown below in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Indicative photos of sensors positioning on a standing (left) and on a Lying (right) person.

To ease the process of sensor-to-leg segment matching, each sensor has been labelled with a unique tag corresponding to the name of the sensor within the application. It is highly advised, but not mandatory, to place the sensors as shown in the table below:

Table 5. Recommended placing of the IMU sensors to leg segments.

No	Description	Sensor Unique tag
1	Left thigh.	DOT6

2	Left leg.	DOT5
3	Left foot.	DOT4
4	Right thigh.	DOT3
5	Right leg.	DOT2
6	Right foot.	DOT1

4.4. Activity recording

During this phase the participating volunteer will perform a series of physiotherapy exercises with its lower limbs, and IMU and video data will be recorded.

Exercises will be performed in three positions: Lying, Sitting and Standing, with various exercises for each position (Table 6, Table 7, Table 8). If both legs are involved, start with the left leg and then move to the right. Pause for the same duration as each repetition between repetitions. It is critical the volunteer has the default pose prior exercise recording.

If, at any point, the volunteer feels discomfort of any kind, he/she has the right to skip the current exercise and/or terminate the visit. The tables below summarize the steps and the exercises to be performed per position.

Table 6. Steps for recording exercises at the Lying position.

Step	Description	Photo
Preparation steps		
1	Place front view (1) and side (2) view cameras to the appropriate positions based on the predefined labeled spots on the floor (3).	
2	Let volunteer lie down	
3	Ensure field of view does not record facial data.	

- 4 Navigate to application’s “Main” tab. In the “IMU Vector Viewer” (1), select the “Lying” pose from the drop-down menu (2). The lying exercises and their variations should appear on the drop-down menus as shown in (3).

- 5 Ensure the appropriate saving directory has been selected and the “Patient ID” (i.e. GRX-XXX) has been filled correct. Select an exercise from list below and the respective variation using the label ID drop down menu. Press the “Start Recording” button and guide the patient to acquire the correct pose in the 3-second countdown and to remain still. Prompt the patient to start the exercises when the “Recording” status appears (1).

Perform 5 repeats of each exercise or exercise variation.

Press the “Stop Recording” button to save the recording when exercise is finished.

Continue to the next exercise when the “Ready for recording” appears.

Exercises sequence		
Exercise	Variation Label	
Lying ankle pumps:		
6.1	Lying_Ankle-Pumps_CL	CL
6.2	Lying_Ankle-Pumps_CR	CR
6.3	Lying_Ankle-Pumps_CB	CB
Lying ankle circles (Inward rotation)		
6.4	Lying_Ankle-Circles-Inward_CL	CL
6.5	Lying_Ankle-Circles-Inward_CR	CR
Lying ankle circles (Outward rotation)		
6.6	Lying_Ankle-Circles-Outward_CL	CL
6.7	Lying_Ankle-Circles-Outward_CR	CR
Lying heel slides:		
6.8	Lying_Heel-Slides_CL	CL
6.9	Lying_Heel-Slides_CR	CR
6.10	Lying_Heel-Slides_CB	CB
Lying straight leg raises:		
6.11	Lying_Straight-Leg-Raises_CL	CL

6.12	Lying_Straight-Leg-Raises_CR	CR
6.13	Lying_Straight-Leg-Raises_IL	IL
6.14	Lying_Straight-Leg-Raises_IR	IR

Lying supine hip abduction:

6.15	Lying_Supine-Hip-Abduction_CL	CL
6.16	Lying_Supine-Hip-Abduction_CR	CR
6.17	Lying_Supine-Hip-Abduction_IL	IL
6.18	Lying_Supine-Hip-Abduction_IR	IR

Lying supine heel taps:

6.19	Lying_Supine-Heel-Taps_CL	CL
6.20	Lying_Supine-Heel-Taps_CR	CR
6.21	Lying_Supine-Heel-Taps_CB	CB

Table 7. Steps for recording exercises at the sitting position.

Step	Description	Photo
Preparation steps		
7	Place front view (1) and side (2) view cameras to the appropriate positions based on the predefined labeled spots on the floor (3).	
8	Let volunteer sit	
9	Ensure field of view does not record facial data	

- 10 Navigate to application’s “Main” tab. In the “IMU Vector Viewer” (1), select the “Sitting” pose from the drop-down menu (2). The sitting exercises and their variations should appear on the drop-down menus as shown in (3).

- 11 Ensure the appropriate saving directory has been selected and the “Patient ID” has been filled correct. Select an exercise from list below and the respective variation using the label ID drop down menu. Press the “Start Recording” button and guide the patient to acquire the correct pose in the 3-second countdown and to remain still. Prompt the patient to start the exercises when the “Recording” status appears (1).

Perform 5 repeats of each exercise or exercise variation.

Press the “Stop Recording” button to save the recording when exercise is finished.

Continue to the next exercise when the “Ready for recording” appears.

Exercises sequence		
Exercise	Variation Label	
Sitting toe-taps (tiptoe):		
12.1	Sitting_Toe-Taps_CL	CL
12.2	Sitting_Toe-Taps_CR	CR
12.3	Sitting_Toe-Taps_CB	CB
12.4	Sitting_Toe-Taps_IL	IL
12.5	Sitting_Toe-Taps_IR	IR
12.6	Sitting_Toe-Taps_CB	CB
Sitting heel raises:		
12.7	Sitting_Heel-Raises_CL	CL
12.8	Sitting_Heel-Raises_CR	CR
12.9	Sitting_Heel-Raises_CB	CB
12.10	Sitting_Heel-Raises_IL	IL
12.11	Sitting_Heel-Raises_IR	IR
12.12	Sitting_Heel-Raises_IB	IB
Sitting ankle pumps:		
12.13	Sitting_Ankle-Pumps_CL	CL

- 12.14 Sitting_Ankle-Pumps_CR CR
- 12.15 Sitting_Ankle-Pumps_CB CB

Sitting ankle circles (Inward rotation):

- 12.16 Sitting-Ankle-Circles-Inward_CL CL
- 12.17 Sitting-Ankle-Circles-Inward_CR CR

Sitting ankle circles (Outward rotation):

- 12.18 Sitting-Ankle-Circles-Outward_CL CL
- 12.19 Sitting-Ankle-Circles-Outward_CR CR

Sitting knee extensions:

- 12.20 Sitting_Knee-Extensions_CL CL
- 12.21 Sitting_Knee-Extensions_CR CR
- 12.22 Sitting_Knee-Extensions_IL IL
- 12.23 Sitting_Knee-Extensions_IR IR

Sitting knee marches:

- 12.24 Sitting_Knee-Marches_CL CL
- 12.25 Sitting_Knee-Marches_CR CR

Table 8. Steps for recording exercises at the standing position.

Step	Description	Photo
Preparation steps		
13	Place front view (1) and side (2) view cameras to the appropriate positions based on the predefined labeled spots on the floor (3).	
14	Let volunteer stand still with legs slightly open.	
15	Ensure field of view does not record facial data	

16 Navigate to application’s “Main” tab. In the “IMU Vector Viewer” (1), select the “Lying” pose from the drop-down menu (2). The lying exercises and their variations should appear on the drop-down menus as shown in (3).

17 Ensure the appropriate saving directory has been selected and the “Patient ID” has been filled correct. Select an exercise from list below and the respective variation using the label ID drop down menu. Press the “Start Recording” button and guide the patient to acquire the correct pose in the 3-second countdown and to remain still. Prompt the patient to start the exercises when the “Recording” status appears (1).

Perform 5 repeats of each exercise or exercise variation.
 Press the “Stop Recording” button to save the recording when exercise is finished.
 Continue to the next exercise when the “Ready for recording” appears.

Exercises sequence		
Exercise		Variation Label
Standing toe raises:		
18.1	Standing_Toe-Raises_CL	CL
18.2	Standing_Toe-Raises_CR	CR
18.3	Standing_Toe-Raises_CB	CB
18.4	Standing_Toe-Raises_IL	IL
18.5	Standing_Toe-Raises_IR	IR
18.6	Standing_Toe-Raises_IB	IB
Standing heel raises:		
18.7	Standing_Heel-Raises_CL	CL
18.8	Standing_Heel-Raises_CR	CR
Standing knee marches:		
18.9	Standing_Knee-Marches_CL	CL
18.10	Standing_Knee-Marches_CR	CR
Standing hip abductions:		
18.11	Standing_Hip-Abductions_CL	CL
18.12	Standing_Hip-Abductions_CR	CR

Standing mini squats:

18.13 Standing_Mini_Squats_CB CB

Each exercise can be performed more than once if required.

4.5. Release of volunteer

After completing all steps of section 4 above ensure all information required by the case report (CRF) form have been filled out and release the volunteer afterwards.

5. Upload recorded data

This section describes the steps for uploading the recorded data to the electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) and the activity data to the private SharePoint. These steps do not require the presence of the volunteer.

5.1. Activity data evaluation

Inspect the file names of the recorded data ensuring proper naming according to each volunteers unique ID. Inspect the video to make sure no facial characteristics have been recorded that will allow volunteers identification.

5.2. Activity data uploading

Compress the recorded files in a .zip file. Name the file with each volunteer's unique ID (i.e. GRX-XXX). Upload the files to the private Study B2 SharePoint. Ensure the file has been uploaded successfully.

5.3. Upload data to eCRF

Browse to the eCRF page and login with the personal credentials. Add a new subject using each volunteer's unique ID. Fill all the details required by the eCRF based on ICF and the physical Case Report Form. Create a link of the uploaded file in the SharePoint and add it to the final tab of the eCRF.

Ensure all data have been filled properly. Activate the "Mark CRF Complete" checkbox and press save to finalize data uploading.